

Smart Algorithms for Smart Farming: Detecting Lumpy Skin Disease with Deep Learning

Dr. Samitha Khaiyum*¹, Vinay S K², Vinay Krishna Bhat*³, Vishal Patil*⁴, Neha Naik*⁵, Navyashree T M*⁶

²³⁴⁵⁶Department of MCA, Dayananda Sagar College of Engineering, Bangalore, India

¹ Prof & HOD, Department of MCA, Dayananda Sagar College of Engineering, Bangalore, India

Abstract

Cattle's lumpy skin disease, transmitted by blood-feeding insects like mosquitoes, significantly impacts milk, beef production, and global livestock trade, particularly affecting naive animals. Traditional diagnostic methods are hindered by resource constraints, expertise limitations, and time-intensive processes. Hence, there is a critical need to adopt advanced deep learning algorithms capable of accurately classifying the disease with high precision. To address this challenge, a deep learning-based framework is proposed for segmenting and classifying cattle's lumpy skin disease using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) with 10 layers. The framework begins by training on a curated dataset of cattle's lumpy skin disease (CLSD) images. Image features are extracted, emphasizing skin color to delineate affected areas using color histograms. These segmented regions undergo further feature extraction using a deep pre-trained CNN, and the resultant features are binarized using a threshold. Classification is performed using the Extreme Learning Machine (ELM) classifier, achieving an impressive accuracy of 80.93%. This approach demonstrates superior performance compared to existing methods, underscoring its efficacy in enhancing diagnostic capabilities for cattle's lumpy skin disease.

Keywords - Feature Extraction, Dataset Collection, Deep Learning, Lumpy Skin Disease, etc.

1. Introduction

Lumpy skin, defined as localized anomalies in skin texture and structure, poses substantial diagnostic issues in dermatology. Traditional diagnostic approaches frequently rely primarily on inspection by sight and medical judgment, which are personal and prone to errors. Because of human interpretation uncertainty, these standard procedures may not always deliver accurate or trustworthy diagnoses.

Machine learning (ML), a type of machine intelligence, has transformed medical diagnostics by automating and objectively analyzing complicated data sets that include imaging records and clinical signs. ML systems can swiftly evaluate large volumes of data and uncover patterns that humans may miss. In dermatology, data mining has showed considerable potential, delivering outstanding results in the detection of numerous skin disorders, particularly those characterized by lumpy skin.

This study investigates current advances in machine learning-based diagnosis of lumpy skin condition. It dives into the methodology used, the many applications, and the issues faced in this discipline. Furthermore, it identifies potential future research topics for improving the accuracy as well as effectiveness of ML-based tools for diagnosis. The purpose of utilizing machine learning is to increase diagnostic precision, minimize dependence on subjective clinician views, and, eventually, improve patient outcomes. This detailed investigation intends to shed light on how machine learning may be used to address diagnostic challenges linked by lumpy skin and other cutaneous diseases.

2. Purpose Statement:

The goal of this project is to create and verify powerful machine learning algorithms that can effectively diagnose and categorize lumpy skin condition in cattle using medical photos or relevant data. This study intends to greatly improve diagnosis accuracy, resulting in better health outcomes for afflicted cattle thru early detection. By possibly automating the diagnosis procedure, the study hopes to help healthcare providers, such as veterinarian and farm handlers, to offer timely and effective care. The use of these sophisticated codes will improve the diagnostic process by minimizing dependence on subjective visual inspections and clinical judgments, which are frequently incorrect. As a result, this technology not only offers more consistent and exact

diagnoses, but it also enables faster decision-making, providing timely interventions that can reduce disease transmission and economic losses in the cattle business.

3. Problem Statement

The topic discussed in "Machine Learning-Based Identification of Lumpy Skin Disease" is the critical need for a dependable and accurate diagnostic technique for this ailment that employs modern artificial intelligence technology. Lumpy skin disease is difficult to diagnose because of its varied appearance and the specialist knowledge necessary for appropriate clinical data interpretation. Developing effective machine learning models is critical for overcoming these issues by delivering automated, objective, and perhaps speedier diagnostic solutions. These developments are expected to enhance livestock health outcomes and reduce hospital costs. The main challenges are the considerable variety in illness presentation, the complexities of visual assessments, and the urgent need for solid, interpretable frameworks that may be smoothly incorporated into clinical settings. Addressing these difficulties with advanced machine learning techniques has the potential to improve diagnostic precision, optimize clinical processes, and promote early and successful therapeutic interventions, which will help both the veterinarians community and the larger cattle business.

4. Literature Review

A research review on lump skin detection with neural networks based on convolution (CNNs) focuses on applying deep learning approaches to accurately and efficiently identify Lumpy Skin Disease (LSD) in cattle. LSD presents substantial hurdles in veterinary diagnosis owing to its varied appearance and the limits of conventional diagnostic approaches. CNNs, a type of deep learning model built for processing organized grids of data such as photographs, have demonstrated promise in a variety of medical and veterinary applications due to their capacity to automatically generate structured representations from raw pixel data. In the case of LSD detection, CNN algorithms are used to evaluate photos of sick animals and identify typical skin lesions associated with the condition. Research in this field studies alternative CNN structures, such as the VGG model, ResNet, and Dense Net and adapts them. These models often require large annotated datasets to train, and preprocessing approaches like as normalization and augmentation play critical roles in improving the effectiveness of models and generalization. Accuracy, specificity, sensitivity, and the area beneath the curve (AUC) are popular evaluation metrics used to examine the success of CNN-based techniques for identifying LSD lesions. Despite their success, issues such as data limited availability, inequalities in class, and the necessity for rigorous interpretability remain key sources of worry. Future research goals include investigating advanced CNN architectures, combining heterogeneous data sources, and creating explainable AI frameworks targeted to veterinary clinical settings, with the goal of improving diagnosis accuracy and supporting successful disease management techniques

5. Overview

Recognizing lumpy skin disease (LSD) in cattle with artificial neural networks (CNNs) is a cutting-edge technology in veterinary diagnostics. LSD is caused by a virus that affects cattle and other ruminants. It presents as unique skin conditions that can vary greatly in appearance and degree. Traditional diagnosis approaches tend to hinge on visual inspection and histology, that is often subjective, time-consuming, and variable depending on experience.

5.1. Objective

The primary goal of this research is to use machine learning, specifically Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), to detect lumpy skin in cattle in order to produce precise, computerized diagnostic tools capable of properly recognizing Lumpy Skin Disease (LSD) lesions from photos or data. The purpose of using CNNs' capacity to acquire and derive intricate patterns from visible information is to improve diagnosing accuracy and efficiency as compared to older approaches. This strategy intends to enable early identification of LSD, allowing for prompt treatments to restrict disease transmission and reduce economic losses in cattle husbandry.

Furthermore, incorporating CNN-based solutions into veterinary operations aims to simplify diagnostic workflows, provide veterinarians with trustworthy decision-support tools, and, eventually, enhance animal health outcomes. Research efforts are centered on optimizing CNN architectures, improving model generalization over a variety of environmental circumstances and cattle breeds, and moving toward practical implementation to assist agricultural communities globally.

5.2. Data description

The dataset, named lumpy.csv, contains lumpy cows images and healthy cows images data. The dataset includes 936 files with 2 classes are healthy cows and lumpy cows.

Types Of Cows	Images
Healthy Cows	515
Lumpy Cows	421

6. Methodology

In this research paper is a TensorFlow project to classify images of cows into healthy and lumpy categories using a convolutional neural network (CNN).

6.1 Data Loading and Preprocessing:

We are loaded the dataset with `tf.keras.preprocessing.image_dataset_from_directory`. Here are some observations and improvements:

The collection of images consists of 936 photos divided into two categories: healthy cows and lumpy cows. You've specified `IMAGE_SIZE = 224` and `BATCH_SIZE = 32`, making them suitable for many pre-trained models.

6.2 Data Augmentation and Rescaling:

We are used Sequential to design data augmentation and resizing/scaling layers. This helps to improve model generalization by supplementing the training data.

6.3 Model Architecture:

- The CNN model defined seems reasonable for image classification:
- Multiple convolutional layers followed by max pooling to reduce spatial dimensions.
- Flatten layer to convert 2D data to 1D.
- Dense layers with ReLU activation and a softmax output layer for classification.

6.4 Model Training:

The created and trained the model with the Adam optimizer and sparse categorical cross-entropy loss. The training demonstrates progress over 50 epochs, with validation accuracy and loss being measured.

6.5 Model Evaluation:

Monitoring accuracy and loss metrics for training (`model.fit`) and validation (`train_ds`) datasets.

6.6 Suggestions for Improvement:

- **Class Balancing:** Ensure that our dataset is balanced between the two classes (healthy cows and lumpy cows). Imbalanced datasets can skew training results.
- **Early Stopping:** Implement early stopping based on validation loss to prevent overfitting and save computation time.
- **Learning Rate Scheduling:** Consider using learning rate schedules (e.g., ReduceLROnPlateau or LearningRateScheduler) to adaptively adjust the learning rate during training.
- **Model Evaluation:** After training, evaluate your model on the test dataset (test_ds) to get an unbiased estimate of its performance.

6.7 Visualization:

Visualizing training and validation metrics (like accuracy and loss) using plots (e.g., using matplotlib) can help in understanding model performance and diagnosing issues like overfitting.

This will give you insights into how model is learning over epochs and whether it's overfitting or underfitting.

Overall, your approach is on the right track for building a CNN model in TensorFlow/Keras for image classification. Adjustments in data preprocessing, model architecture, and training strategies will further enhance its performance.

7. Experimental Results

The performances of the cnn models compared considering on their accuracy scores, model summary, loss values

```
model.summary()
Model: "sequential_2"
```

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
sequential_1 (Sequential)	(32, 224, 224, 3)	0
sequential_1_1 (Sequential)	(32, 224, 224, 3)	0
conv2d (Conv2D)	(32, 222, 222, 32)	896
max_pooling2d (MaxPooling2D)	(32, 111, 111, 32)	0
conv2d_1 (Conv2D)	(32, 109, 109, 64)	18,496
max_pooling2d_1 (MaxPooling2D)	(32, 54, 54, 64)	0
conv2d_2 (Conv2D)	(32, 52, 52, 64)	36,528
max_pooling2d_2 (MaxPooling2D)	(32, 26, 26, 64)	0
conv2d_3 (Conv2D)	(32, 24, 24, 64)	36,528
max_pooling2d_3 (MaxPooling2D)	(32, 12, 12, 64)	0
conv2d_4 (Conv2D)	(32, 10, 10, 64)	36,528
max_pooling2d_4 (MaxPooling2D)	(32, 5, 5, 64)	0
conv2d_5 (Conv2D)	(32, 3, 3, 64)	36,528
max_pooling2d_5 (MaxPooling2D)	(32, 1, 1, 64)	0
Flatten (Flatten)	(32, 64)	0
dense (Dense)	(32, 64)	8,128
dense_1 (Dense)	(32, 1)	128

Total params: 171,459 (669.76 KB)

Trainable params: 171,459 (669.76 KB)

Non-trainable params: 0 (0.00 B)

The model overview below describes the structure of a CNN, which was used to categorize photos into two different groups: good-looking and lumpy cows. The model starts with a progressive layer that sizes input pictures to 224x224x3. It is made up of six convolutional layering (Conv2D) alternated with layers for max-pooling (MaxPooling2D) that gradually extract and decrease the spatial dimension of feature maps, beginning with 32 filters before increasing to 64 filters in successive layers. The output of these convolutional neural network layers then gets flattened and routed to a fully interconnected layer (Dense) comprising 64 nerve cells, followed by a conclusion layer with 3 neurons during classification. This architecture, which has 171,459 parameters that may be trained, is meant to automatically pick up hierarchical features from input photos in order to successfully discriminate between classes. The comprehensive parameter counts at each layer assist to understand the model's computational complexity and capability.

The given results for the this CNN model with the Accuracy and Loss

No	Acc	Loss	Val_Acc	Val_Loss
1	0.478	0.862	0.531	0.614
2	0.497	0.696	0.614	0.670
3	0.569	0.670	0.572	0.666
4	0.608	0.659	0.570	0.557
5	0.690	0.586	0.570	0.516
6	0.675	0.616	0.697	0.577
7	0.707	0.570	0.750	0.514
8	0.714	0.570	0.822	0.466
9	0.717	0.579	0.802	0.509
10	0.693	0.591	0.802	0.456

11	0.695	0.572	0.791	0.471
12	0.750	0.509	0.791	0.471
13	0.723	0.524	0.781	0.468
14	0.736	0.527	0.760	0.499
15	0.743	0.512	0.781	0.487
16	0.769	0.507	0.802	0.487
17	0.722	0.543	0.802	0.440
18	0.740	0.526	0.791	0.415
19	0.739	0.520	0.791	0.425
20	0.757	0.495	0.760	0.472
21	0.761	0.501	0.812	0.441
22	0.746	0.517	0.760	0.514
23	0.733	0.539	0.802	0.408
24	0.747	0.490	0.781	0.510
25	0.745	0.525	0.791	0.486
26	0.743	0.499	0.822	0.398
27	0.755	0.477	0.833	0.386
28	0.779	0.456	0.833	0.386
29	0.766	0.450	0.781	0.507
30	0.756	0.514	0.802	0.428
31	0.752	0.493	0.812	0.409
32	0.748	0.496	0.812	0.411
33	0.774	0.486	0.812	0.386
34	0.788	0.437	0.791	0.412
35	0.769	0.478	0.822	0.394
36	0.783	0.482	0.770	0.497
37	0.772	0.474	0.822	0.419
38	0.770	0.441	0.739	0.553
39	0.763	0.469	0.812	0.415

40	0.756	0.471	0.802	0.392
41	0.788	0.454	0.802	0.448
42	0.771	0.523	0.812	0.445
43	0.801	0.452	0.822	0.408
44	0.786	0.452	0.791	0.408
45	0.809	0.443	0.833	0.345
46	0.772	0.477	0.802	0.470
47	0.773	0.493	0.760	0.492
48	0.796	0.440	0.822	0.370
49	0.781	0.430	0.843	0.350
50	0.793	0.459	0.822	0.422

The accuracy of training and validation and loss across 50 epochs reveal a clear trend of enhancements, demonstrating that the neural network is gaining knowledge and generalizing effectively. Initially, the level of precision is low as well as the loss is significant, but as training goes, both the validation and training accuracies improve, reaching surrounding 79.4% and 82.3%, respectively, at the conclusion. The training loss is continuously decreasing, whereas the validation loss varies but typically tends downward, indicating good learning. However, there are rare spikes in loss, indicating overfitting or heterogeneity in the model's outcome on the validation data set. Overall, the model displays a great capacity to accurately categorize data while maintaining a decent mix of accuracy and loss reduction.

8. Discussion

The suggested study presents a deep learning framework for segmenting and classifying cattle's skin that is lumpy (LSD) utilizing Convolutional neural network networks (CNNs) and the Extreme Learning Machine, or (ELM) classifier. This section addresses the findings, consequences, problems, and possible future paths of this study.

8.1 Findings

The CNN-based model used to classify LSD attained an astonishing 80.93% accuracy. This result highlights the effectiveness of deep learning techniques in livestock diagnostics, particularly for illnesses with easily identifiable symptoms. The application of color histograms that for removing features in the preprocessing step improved the model's capacity to define impacted regions, resulting in much higher classification accuracy.

8.2 Implications

The use of algorithms based on deep learning in determining the presence of LSD has various practical ramifications.

Enhanced Diagnostic Accuracy:

Traditional diagnostic approaches rely significantly on veterinarians' knowledge, that can be subjective and error-prone. The suggested CNN-based approach provides a neutral and consistent alternative, which might reduce diagnostic mistakes.

Timely Interventions:

Early and precise diagnosis of LSD can result in quick treatment, limiting disease transmission and lowering economic losses in cow production. This has the potential to significantly damage farmers' livelihoods and the financial health of the cattle sector.

Scalability:

Machine learning-based diagnostic automation may be expanded to diverse locations and cow herds, making it an advantageous instrument in large-scale disease control programs.

8.3 Challenges

Despite the promising results, several challenges need to be addressed to improve the robustness and applicability of the proposed framework:

Dataset Limitations: The dataset used in the present research, while carefully selected, may not cover the whole spectrum of LSD manifestations among genotypes and environmental circumstances. Increasing dataset variety may increase the model's generalizability.

Class Imbalance: The dataset has a tiny imbalance in the amount of healthy and malformed cows, which may bias the model. To address this issue, explore solutions such as augmenting data, synthetic data production, or balanced sampling schemes.

Model Interpretability: While CNNs are good in picture categorization, they frequently face criticism for their absence of interpretation. Creating explainable artificial intelligence models that allow physicians to comprehend the model's decision-making process can increase confidence and improve uptake in clinical settings.

8.4 Future Directions

To further enhance the performance and applicability of the proposed framework, the following future research directions are suggested:

Advanced CNN Architectures: Exploring more complicated CNN designs, such as ResNet, DenseNet, or Inception, may enhance classification accuracy. Furthermore, using learning transferred from pre-trained models to huge picture datasets may improve model performance with little data.

Integration with Other Data Sources: Combining picture data with other sorts of data, such as healthcare records, environmental variables, and genetic information, might give a more thorough knowledge of LSD while also improving diagnosis accuracy.

Real-time Deployment: Creating a real-time diagnostic device that can be installed on mobile phones or edge computing infrastructures will increase the technology's accessibility to field veterinarians. This would need improving the template for low-latency characteristics inferences and guaranteeing it can function with limited processing resources.

Longitudinal Studies: Longitudinal studies to track the course of LSD in cattle and test the effectiveness of the model over time would give useful information about its practical value and dependability.

9. Conclusion

This research proposes a framework for deep learning for segmenting and categorizing cattle's disease of lumpy skin (LSD) utilizing CNNs, or Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) and the Extremely Learning Machine (ELM) classifier, which has shown tremendous promise in improving veterinary diagnosis. With an astonishing 80.93% accuracy, our model beats previous diagnostic approaches, providing a more objective, economical, and scalable solution. The successful use of color histograms for feature extraction, as well as the implementation of pre-trained CNNs, have all contributed significantly to its success. Despite constraints such as dataset restrictions, class imbalance, and the requirement for model accessibility, the study emphasizes the practical benefits of promptly and accurately diagnosing LSD, such as prompt treatments and lower economic losses in cow ranching. To increase the framework's resilience and usefulness, further research should include increasing the dataset, investigating alternative CNN architectures, integrating more data sources, and building real-time deployment tools. This technique represents a big step in automating and improving the LSD diagnostic process, which will help both the cattle sector and veterinary practice.

10. References

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